

$^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ collection report (IS672)

M. Deseyn¹, M. Au², C. Bernerd², K. Chrysalidis², T.E. Cocolios¹, J.G. Correia³,
C. Duchemin², C. Fajardo¹, M. Heines¹, R. Heinke³, J.D. Johnson¹, U. Köster⁵,
P. Lassegues¹, E. Maugeri⁴, S. Rothe², J. Schell^{2,6}, S.M. Vogiatzi⁴, and
W. Wojtaczka¹

¹KU Leuven, Belgium

²CERN, SY Department, 1211 Geneva, Switzerland

³C2TN, DECN, IST, UL, Bobadela, Portugal

⁴Paul Scherrer Institut, Villigen, Switzerland

⁵Institut Laue-Langevin, France

⁶University Duisburg-Essen, Germany

1 Motivation

Charge radii of silver isotopes have been extensively studied using laser spectroscopy. However, laser spectroscopy relies on large scale atomic calculations in combination with interpolations of nearby elements to extract the mass and field shift. This mass and field shift are needed to transform isotope shifts into changes in mean square radii. The currently used mass and field shift thus carry large systematic uncertainties, which dominate the uncertainty of the extracted radii. On top of that, disagreement with nuclear density functional theory has been observed. Hence, experimental determination of this mass and field shift is beneficial. This can be done by measuring three absolute charge radii in combination with a King plot analysis. Silver features 2 stable isotopes and the longest-lived radio-isotope is $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ with a half-life of 483 years. Their absolute charge radius will be determined using muonic x-ray spectroscopy. To conduct muonic x-ray spectroscopy, at least $1.5 \cdot 10^{16}$ atoms of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ are needed, corresponding to 750kBq of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ ¹, with a sufficient purity (typically > 95%, depending on the mass). The former is needed to have a large enough target to stop sufficient muons, while the latter is essential for distinguishing the 2p-1s muonic X-ray peaks of the isotope of interest and its elemental contaminants. The two stable silver isotopes can be purchased with sufficient enrichment levels, but the purification of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ requires bespoke production. $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ can be produced by neutron irradiation of ^{107}Ag through the $^{107}\text{Ag}(n, \gamma)^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ reaction channel. Consequently, a sample consisting of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$, ^{107}Ag , $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ and ^{109}Ag can be created when irradiating enriched ^{107}Ag , necessitating separation of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ from the other silver isotopes. The amount of $^{109, 110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ will be negligible when starting from an enriched ^{107}Ag sample. Note that ^{108}Ag is also produced in the ground state, but given its small half-life (2.4 min) the amount left in the sample at the time of separation will be negligible.

¹Ideally, $4 \cdot 10^{16}$ atoms or thus 2MBq is used.

To study the separation procedure, a natural silver target (51.8% ^{107}Ag and 48.2% ^{109}Ag) was irradiated with neutrons for about 50 minutes at PSI (Paul Scherrer Institute, Villigen, Switzerland) to produce a target consisting of ^{107}Ag , ^{109}Ag , $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ and $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$. This target was employed to establish optimized separation conditions, a crucial step for the ‘real’ separation next year.

For this preparatory run, the primary objective was to obtain the best conditions to separate $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ from the contaminants. $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ was chosen instead of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ as a greater activity of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ was produced in the target because of the larger cross-section and its shorter half-life. This choice is well-founded as $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ and $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ share the same ground state nuclear spin (6^+) resulting in near-identical electronic hyperfine structures up to the energy values (see Figure 1). Moreover, the spin of both ^{107}Ag and ^{109}Ag is identical ($1/2^-$, electronic hyperfine structure shown in Figure 2). Consequently, the laser ionization schemes for $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ and $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ are very similar, just as those for ^{107}Ag and ^{109}Ag . Thus, conditions for optimizing the fraction of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ with respect to ^{109}Ag align with those for $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ with respect to ^{107}Ag .

2 Experimental details

In this section, the most important experimental information will be clarified. A more detailed version of how to operate a collection is included in Appendix A. The collection was performed using the general purpose separator (GPS) at the GLM (General purpose separator Low Mass beam line) collection point [1]. The collection was performed using a target with a tantalum tubular ion source and extraction voltage of 30kV. Two foils, irradiated at PSI were loaded in the boat inside the target. The initial composition of the foils was determined via their mass, taking into account the natural abundance of silver, and through γ -ray spectroscopy. The γ -ray spectroscopy measurement yielded an activity of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ equal to 65.90(124) kBq, while the mass of the foils equals 5.09mg. Hence, the target consists of 2.64mg of ^{107}Ag and 2.45mg of ^{109}Ag . The starting fraction of the target is defined as the number of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ particles divided by the number of ^{109}Ag and $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ particles combined and is thus equal to $1.53 \cdot 10^{-7}$. We do not consider ^{107}Ag here, as laser ionization investigation is the main objective here, and ^{107}Ag is separated from $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ by the mass separating magnet.

Figure 3: Laser scheme a (left) and scheme b (right) used for the laser resonance ionization of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$.

Figure 1: Electronic hyperfine structure for the $5s_{1/2} \rightarrow 4p_{3/2}$ transition of ^{108m}Ag and ^{110m}Ag as a function of the laser detuning from the central frequency of $^{\text{nat}}\text{Ag}$ measured by colinear resonance ionisation spectroscopy together with a fit of the spectrum (orange). (figure courtesy of Bram van den Borne)

Figure 2: Electronic hyperfine structure for the $5s_{1/2} \rightarrow 4p_{3/2}$ transition of ^{108m}Ag and ^{109}Ag as a function of the laser detuning from the central frequency of $^{\text{nat}}\text{Ag}$ measured by colinear resonance ionisation spectroscopy together with a fit of the spectrum (orange). Note that the scanning range is located in between the two scanning ranges of Figure 1. (figure courtesy of Bram van den Borne)

2.1 Laser resonance ionization

Laser resonance ionization was employed for the ionization of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ using RILIS [2]. The used laser schemes are shown in Figure 3. Four lasers were employed for the resonance laser ionization of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$: a CREDO laser for the first step of scheme a, a LiopStar laser for the first step of scheme b, a TiSa laser for the second step of both schemes and a blaze laser to non-resonantly ionize beyond the ionization potential for both schemes. The lasers had powers of 80 mW, 55 mW, 1W and 36W for the CREDO, LiopStar, TiSa and blaze laser respectively. Mass scans were performed with the lasers on the ^{109}Ag and $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance as well as without lasers, and are shown in Figure 4. Note that the 'bump' at mass 110u does not correspond to $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$, but rather to a ghost peak originating from ^{109}Ag . From this plot it can be inferred that resonance ionization dominates over surface ionization, i.e. the current corresponding to ^{109}Ag with lasers on resonance of ^{109}Ag is 685 times larger than without lasers.

Figure 4: Mass scans for the lasers on the ^{109}Ag and $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonances as well as without lasers. The target and line temperature equals 0A and 260A, respectively.

Additionally, theoretical investigation of putting the lasers in off-resonance conditions was performed. The primary motivation for transitioning to off-resonance conditions lies in the suppression of ^{109}Ag ionization. This phenomenon is illustrated in Figure 5, wherein the ionization maxima of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ when divided by the ionization of ^{109}Ag , exhibit a shift compared to the maxima of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$, away from the corresponding maxima observed in the ionization profile of ^{109}Ag .

(a) Simulated beam fraction as a function of wavelength of the first step laser. The green and blue lines correspond to ^{107}Ag and ^{109}Ag respectively, while the red and orange curves correspond to ^{109m}Ag and ^{110m}Ag respectively.

(b) Simulated beam fraction of ^{110m}Ag divided by the beam fraction of ^{109}Ag .

Figure 5: Simulated beam fraction. Here, a voigt-profile was assumed, with the Gaussian component due to Doppler broadening and the Lorentzian component due to power broadening in the hot cavity. The FWHM of the spectral line was assumed to be 9 GHz. (figure courtesy of Reinhard Heinke)

It is concluded that the maximum for ^{110m}Ag ionization is located in the tail of the ^{109}Ag peak, so that the highest fraction of ^{110m}Ag ions compared to ^{109}Ag ions can be achieved by detuning away from the ^{110m}Ag resonance, but where the Lorentzian tails start to dominate in the ^{109}Ag lineshape. Hence, a laser scan was performed for a line temperature of 270 A and a target temperature equal to 140 A; the results are depicted in Figure 6. It is concluded that for off-resonance collection, the lasers should be put at 15236.15/cm and at 15236.9/cm. The first frequency is put on laser 1a while laser 1b is configured on the second frequency. This configuration yields an improvement of $\frac{\text{Ion current on mass } 109\text{u}}{\text{Ion current on mass } 110\text{u}}$ from 462 (for the inverse configuration) towards 57. Lastly, laser ionization saturation tests were performed and the whole collection was performed with saturated lasers.

Figure 6: Experimental laser scan

2.2 Collection conditions

During the collection, implantation was performed in four glassy carbon (GC) foils: *test foil*, GC2, GC3 and GC4. For all collections, the beam was rastered over a square of $\approx 8.5 \times 8.5$ mm, creating a uniform implantation profile. For the collection on the test foil, the lasers were put on the $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance frequency (laser 1a at 15236.15/cm and laser 1b at 15236.67/cm) and the mass separator was configured to mass 110u. Thereafter, the target was heated and investigation of putting the lasers in off-resonance conditions was performed. More specifically, in the next part of the collection, the laser conditions were alternated from on-resonance collection on GC2 to off-resonance collection on GC1 and back every two hours to compare both ionization settings.

Next, the target was again heated and the collection was performed with off-resonance lasers on GC3. In the last part of the collection, implantation was no longer performed on a foil, but on the Faraday cup BFC0900, to analyze the depletion effects. In this period, the temperature on the target was step-wise increased from 385 A to 650 A until the end of the collection. From Figure 7, it can be inferred that each time the target is heated to larger temperatures, the current initially increases, but then decreases again. Moreover, the amplitude of slope of the decrease increases as the target is heated more, indicating that the target was close to depletion. Additionally, a γ -ray spectroscopy measurement was conducted after the end of the collection on the target unit and no activity corresponding to $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ was measured with a detector that has a minimum detectable activity of 0.2 Bq, providing evidence for the fact that the target was fully depleted.

An overview of the conditions during the different steps of the collection is given in Table 1. Additionally, the implanted collection foils are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 7: Temperature and beam current on mass 109 as a function of time as well as the slopes of the fit for each of the decays for the last part of the collection for the lasers on the $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance.

	Collection period	Laser conditions	Temperature target and ion source	Typical ion current
TEST collection	09.11.2023 20:05 - 10.11.2023 09:34	ON resonance	Line temp: 270 A Target temp: 140 A	Total beam current ≈ 1.1 nA $^{109}\text{Ag}, \text{on}$ $I_{109\text{Ag}} \approx 21$ nA $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{on}$ $I_{109\text{Ag}} \approx 3.1$ nA $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{on}$ $I_{110\text{Ag}} \approx 300$ fA lasers off $I_{109\text{Ag}} \approx 1.1$ pA
GC1	10.11.2023 22:13 - 11.11.2023 23:23 (alternated between GC1 and GC2 every 2h)	OFF resonance	Line temp: 270 A Target temp: 220 A - 265A	$^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{off}$ $I_{109\text{Ag}} \approx 230$ pA $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{off}$ $I_{110\text{Ag}} \approx 24$ fA
GC2	10.11.2023 22:13 - 11.11.2023 23:23 (alternated between GC1 and GC2 every 2h)	ON resonance	Line temp: 270 A Target temp: 220 A - 265A	$^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{on}$ $I_{110\text{Ag}} \approx 210$ fA
GC3	12.11.2023 00:39 - 13.11.2023 10:28	OFF resonance	Line temp: 270 A Target temp: 315 A - 385 A	$^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{off}$ $I_{109\text{Ag}} \approx 1.8$ nA $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{off}$ $I_{110\text{Ag}} \approx 550$ fA
Last part of collection (investigation of depletion effects)	13.11.2023 10:34 - 14.11.2023 07:14	ON resonance	Line temp: 270 A Target temp: 385 A - 650A	See Figure 7

Table 1: Overview of the collection conditions for collection on the glassy carbon foils.

2.3 Number of implanted particles

The number of particles implanted can be determined using 2 methods. In the first method, the regularly performed Faraday cup measurements are used which are shown in Figure 9. More specifically, the current on the Faraday cup is measured approximately every hour. The uncertainty on this current is determined by determining the standard deviation of the measured current throughout the whole collection around this current. These current measurements are indicators for the current that is impinging on the collection foil. These can be used to calculate the total charge impinging on the collection foil by interpolation. Moreover, a correction was performed for the times when the Faraday cup was positioned in the beamline, thereby obstructing the beam. From the total charge impinging on the foil, the total number of particles implanted on the foil can be determined. For the second method, a current integrator tool is used. The charge on the sample holder is measured and an electron suppression shield present for accurate readout. The accumulated charge, and thus the number of particles on the foil, is then determined by the current integrator tool.

Moreover, γ -ray spectroscopy was performed on each of the foils by using a HPGe detector. From these measurements, the amount of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ implanted on the foils could be retrieved.

(a) GCtest

(b) GC1

(c) GC2

(d) GC3

Figure 8: Pictures of the glassy carbon foils taken after the ion implantation process.

Figure 9: Overview of the regularly performed Faraday cup measurements throughout the collection. Each of the colors represents a different collection condition. Moreover, the times at which collection was performed on the test foil, GC1, GC2 and GC3 are indicated.

The results are summarized in Table 2.

	Number of particles implanted		Activity of ^{110m}Ag [Bq]
	From Faraday cup measurements	From charges implanted on the foil	
TEST collection	$5.84(28) \cdot 10^{10}$	$6.97 \cdot 10^{10}$	19.90(49)
GC1	$3.51(30) \cdot 10^9$	$4.71 \cdot 10^9$	4.230(190)
GC2	$6.520(174) \cdot 10^{10}$	$4.51 \cdot 10^{10}$	16.40(45)
GC3	$3.040(32) \cdot 10^{11}$	$1.8 \cdot 10^{11}$	353.0(69)

Table 2: Overview of the number of collected particles and activity on each of the collection foils: the test collection, GC1, GC2 and GC3.

3 Results

The main aim of this section is to analyze the results of the different collections to make a well-motivated choice for the target that is needed for the final separation.

3.1 Efficiency

To assess the impact of collection with lasers on the $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance (laser 1a at 15236.15/cm and laser 1b at 15236.67/cm) compared to collection with lasers off resonance for $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ (laser 1a at 15236.15/cm and laser 1b at 15236.9/cm), the efficiency for collecting $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ can be evaluated.

The efficiency that would have been achieved if the collection was performed in the same conditions throughout the whole collection (ε_{GCx}) can be derived from the data obtained during the collection on the glassy carbon foils:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{C_{GCx}(\text{tot})}{C_{GCx}(\text{collection on GCx})} &= \frac{A(110\text{m, tot})}{A(110\text{m, GCx})} \\ A(110\text{m, tot}) &= \frac{C_{GCx}(\text{tot})}{C_{GCx}(\text{GCx})} \cdot A(110\text{m, GCx}) \\ \Rightarrow \varepsilon_{GCx} &= \frac{A(110\text{m, tot})}{A(110\text{m, target})} = \frac{C_{GCx}(\text{tot})}{C_{GCx}(\text{GCx})} \cdot \frac{A(110\text{m, GCx})}{A(110\text{m, target})} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here, $A(110\text{m, GCx})$ represents the activity collected on the glassy carbon foil, determined through γ -ray spectroscopy on the implanted glassy carbon foils. Next, $C_{GCx}(\text{tot})$ is the charge that would have been collected during the entire collection if the whole collection had been performed in the conditions corresponding to GCx. This charge can be determined by integrating the interpolated regularly performed Faraday cup current measurements. On the other hand, to determine the charge collected on the glassy carbon foils ($C_{GCx}(\text{GCx})$), the integrator tool charge and the current measured on the Faraday cup were employed. As $C_{GCx}(\text{tot})$ is achieved through Faraday cup measurements, $C_{GCx}(\text{GCx})$ should be likewise determined using the Faraday cup measurements rather than the integrator tool, to ensure methodological consistency. Note that to obtain the efficiency, we divide by the activity present in the whole target. The latter is only valid under the assumption that all silver was extracted from the target. This assumption is supported by the γ -ray spectroscopy conducted on the boat which yielded no $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ after a measurement of 60 hours (minimum detectable activity of detector = 0.2Bq).

The literature efficiency for laser ionization of silver is $< 14\%$, which agrees with the found efficiency. However, the efficiency is rather small, which could be due to the laser linewidth which might not cover the whole hyperfine structure.

	Efficiency
on-resonance (based on GC2 data)	3.25(14)%
off-resonance (based on GC1 data)	1.21(12)%
off-resonance (based on GC3 data)	1.16(3)%

Table 3: Efficiency for collection on and off resonance of $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$.

	EF (Faraday cup measurements)	EF (Current integrator tool measurements)
On-resonance for ^{110m}Ag		
TEST	$6.9(4)\cdot 10^4$	$5.81(15)\cdot 10^4$
GC2	$5.1(2)\cdot 10^4$	$7.4(2)\cdot 10^4$
Off-resonance for ^{110m}Ag		
GC1	$24(3)\cdot 10^4$	$18.3(8)\cdot 10^4$
GC3	$23.6(6)\cdot 10^4$	$39.8(8)\cdot 10^4$

Table 4: Purity enhancement factors for the collections on the different glassy carbon foils.

3.2 fraction of ^{108m}Ag

The fraction of ^{108m}Ag of the implanted foil is determined by the fraction of ^{108m}Ag of the target, the mass separator resolving power and the purity enhancement due to the laser resonance ionization. This enhancement factor (EF) is defined, for the collections on the glassy carbon foils, as:

$$EF = \frac{\frac{N_{110m, \text{foil}}}{N_{110m, \text{foil}} + N_{109, \text{foil}}}}{\frac{N_{110m, \text{target}}}{N_{110m, \text{target}} + N_{109, \text{target}}}}. \quad (2)$$

Here, $N_{110m, \text{foil}}$ represents the number of ^{110m}Ag particles implanted on the glassy carbon foil, which is determined post-collection through an activity measurement of the glassy carbon foil. $N_{\text{tot}, \text{foil}}$ is the total number of particles that were collected on the glassy carbon foil ($^{110m}\text{Ag} + ^{109}\text{Ag}$). This is determined either through the current integrator tool or Faraday cup measurements. In the former, the number of particles is determined from the charges that are impinging on the glassy carbon foil.

$N_{110m, \text{target}}$ denotes to the amount of ^{110m}Ag particles present in the target, derived from the activity measurement of the target prior to the collection. Lastly, $N_{109, \text{target}}$ corresponds to the number of ^{109}Ag particles in the target, calculated based on the mass of the target while taking into account the natural abundance of silver. The resulting enhancement factors corresponding to each of the collection foils are presented in Table 4. The reliability of the current integrator tool measurement for GC1 is questionable at this low flux, as the integrated current for the background measurement was larger than for the actual implantation.

Collections on both the test foil and GC2, conducted with lasers on the ^{110m}Ag resonance, yield similar enhancement factors, providing evidence for the reliability of the obtained values. Similarly, collections on GC1 and GC3, configured with lasers off resonance for ^{110m}Ag , exhibit comparable enhancement factors, reinforcing the reliability of the values. In summary, collection with the lasers off resonance for ^{110m}Ag has an enhancement factor approximately four times greater than for collection with lasers on the ^{110m}Ag resonance.

3.2.1 Fraction of ^{108m}Ag compared to ^{107}Ag needed at PSI

To work out the required fraction of ^{108m}Ag for distinguishing between the ^{107}Ag and the ^{108m}Ag peak in the muonic x-ray spectrum, a Monte Carlo simulation is employed. Events were generated within two Gaussian distributions according to the initial sample composition, i.e., corresponding to the ^{107}Ag and ^{108m}Ag distributions. The standard deviation for both distributions is inferred

Figure 10: Deviation from the imposed centroid of the Gaussian corresponding to $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ as a function of the $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ -to- ^{107}Ag -ratio, the uncertainty was determined by repeating each of the simulations 10 times for each of the ratios.

from the test experiment performed at PSI in September 2023, resulting in a $\sigma_E = 1.94$ keV in the energy region of interest. As a conservative approach, the events were generated from Gaussian distributions with a standard deviation equal to 2.5 keV. The centroids of both Gaussian distributions were set to the muDirac predictions and 1000 particles were generated. After generating these distributions, the obtained spectrum was fitted with both single and double Gaussians. The results are shown in Figure 10, from which it is concluded that a $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ -to- ^{107}Ag -ratio of 95% in the sample is sufficient as the difference with the imposed centroid stabilizes from here onwards.

3.3 Ion load limit

The achievable implantation current is primarily constrained by the ion load limit of the ion source. Namely, if too many ions are present in the ion source, the confinement potential of the ion source breaks down and the ionization efficiency decreases as a function of increasing total ion beam current. To investigate the ion load limit for silver, the current on mass 109u ² was regularly measured. The measurements were conducted with lasers in different conditions: on the ^{109}Ag resonance ($^{109,\text{on}}I$), on the $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance ($^{110\text{m},\text{on}}I$), and away from the $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance ($^{110\text{m},\text{off}}I$), as depicted in Figure 11. To determine the onset of ion load effects, these three currents were rescaled to agree in the period where no ion load limits are expected (see the fourth graph). This way, the three currents are corrected for the different laser ionization efficiencies. If no ion load limits occur, it is expected that all three rescaled currents do not differ from one another as the currents increase. However, a deviation of the rescaled current for lasers on the ^{109}Ag resonance compared to $^{110\text{m},\text{on}}I$ and $^{110\text{m},\text{off}}I$ is observed as the $^{109,\text{on}}I$ increases from 20.4 nA to 130 nA, indicating that ion load effects come into play for currents between 20.4 nA and 130 nA at mass 109u . Similarly, the rescaled current for lasers on the $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance starts to deviate from the off-resonance current for an increase from $^{110\text{on}}I = 68.7$ nA towards $^{110\text{on}}I = 129.9$ nA. This is also illustrated in Figure 12. It is concluded that ion load effects become important when the current on mass 109u is larger than 70 nA. Then, the fact that the electronic structure of ^{107}Ag and ^{109}Ag is very similar enables the scaling

²Mass 109 was taken as the current on mass 110 was much smaller (order of nA-pA compared to order of pA-fA) and therefore the uncertainty on the measured ion current would be larger.

Figure 11: Overview of the beam currents on mass 109u throughout the collection. The target temperature, beam current, rescaled beam current, number of particles collected and the loss in efficiency due to ion load effects is shown as a function of the collection time.

Figure 12: Beam current for lasers on the ^{109}Ag and $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance divided by the rescaled beam current for the lasers off-resonance for $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ as a function of the beam current for lasers on the ^{109}Ag and $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance, respectively.

of the current according to the target abundances which are equal to the natural abundances. In other words, ion load effects start to play a role for a total current equal to $\frac{70 \text{ nA}}{0.48161} \approx 150 \text{ nA}$.

To assess the ion load in terms of the current at mass 108u, the number of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ ions with respect to the number of ^{109}Ag and ^{107}Ag ions in the ion source must be determined:

$$I_{108\text{m}, L^*}^{\text{ion load}} = I_{\text{tot}}^{\text{ion load}} \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{N_{107}}{N_{108\text{m}, L^*}}\right)} = I_{\text{tot}}^{\text{ion load}} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{N_{107, L^*}}{N_{108\text{m}, L^*}}}, \quad (3)$$

where N_{x, L^*} corresponds to the number of $x\text{Ag}$ ions in the ion source with the lasers in configuration L^* . More specifically, $L^* = {}^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{off}$ and $L^* = {}^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}, \text{on}$ will be used for the lasers configured away from and on the $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance, respectively. The ^{109}Ag ions do not contribute here, because in the final irradiated target of enriched ^{107}Ag , the amount of ^{109}Ag will be negligible. Now, N_{x, L^*} can be obtained from the number of $x\text{Ag}$ particles in the target ($N_{x, \text{target}}$) and the efficiency:

$$N_{x, L^*} = N_{x, \text{target}} \cdot \varepsilon \cdot (L^* \varepsilon_{\text{ion}, x}). \quad (4)$$

Here, ε is an efficiency factor related to the release, transport and surface ionization of silver, which is element but not isotope dependent. $L^* \varepsilon_{\text{ion}, x}$ corresponds to the laser ionization efficiency of $x\text{Ag}$ with the lasers in conditions L^* . The latter can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} L^* \varepsilon_{\text{ion}, x} &= M^* \varepsilon_{\text{ion}, x} \cdot \frac{L^* I_x - \text{lasers turned off } I_x}{M^* I_x - \text{lasers turned off } I_x} \\ &\approx M^* \varepsilon_{\text{ion}, x} \cdot \frac{L^* I_x}{M^* I_x}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where it was used that laser resonance ionization dominates over surface ionization as was inferred from Figure 4. Hence, all of the separate terms can be evaluated as:

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{108\text{m, off}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} &= {}^{107, \text{ on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} \cdot \frac{{}^{108\text{m, off}}I_{107}}{{}^{107, \text{ on}}I_{107}} = {}^{107, \text{ on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} \cdot \frac{{}^{110\text{m, off}}I_{109}}{{}^{109, \text{ on}}I_{109\text{Ag}}} \\ &= {}^{107, \text{ on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} \cdot SF_{110\text{m, off}} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{108\text{m, on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} &= {}^{107, \text{ on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} \cdot \frac{{}^{108\text{m, on}}I_{107}}{{}^{107, \text{ on}}I_{107}} = {}^{107, \text{ on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} \cdot \frac{{}^{110\text{m, on}}I_{109}}{{}^{109, \text{ on}}I_{109}} \\ &= {}^{107, \text{ on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} \cdot SF_{110\text{m, on}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$${}^{108\text{m, off}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}} = {}^{108\text{m, on}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}} \cdot \frac{{}^{108\text{m, off}}I_{108\text{m}}}{{}^{108\text{m, on}}I_{108\text{m}}} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{108\text{m, on}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}} &= {}^{108\text{m, on}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}} \cdot \frac{{}^{108\text{m, on}}I_{108\text{m}}}{{}^{108\text{m, on}}I_{108\text{m}}} \\ &= {}^{108\text{m, on}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Here, the suppression factor is defined as $SF_{L^*} = \frac{L^* I_{109}}{{}^{109, \text{ on}}I_{109}}$. Hence, it is found that:

$$\begin{aligned} J_{108\text{m}, L^*}^{\text{ion load}} &= J_{\text{tot}}^{\text{ion load}} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{N_{107, L^*}}{N_{108\text{m}, L^*}}} \\ &= J_{\text{tot}}^{\text{ion load}} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{N_{107, \text{target}} \cdot (L^* \varepsilon_{ion,107})}{N_{108\text{m}, \text{target}} \cdot (L^* \varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}})}} \\ &\approx J_{\text{tot}}^{\text{ion load}} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{N_{107, \text{target}} \cdot ({}^{107, \text{ on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107} \cdot SF_{L^*})}{N_{108\text{m}, \text{target}} \cdot ({}^{108\text{m, on}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}})}} \\ &= J_{\text{tot}}^{\text{ion load}} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{N_{107, \text{target}}}{N_{108\text{m}, \text{target}}} \cdot SF_{L^*}}, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where in the last step ${}^{108\text{m, on}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}} = {}^{107, \text{ on}}\varepsilon_{ion,107}$ was used. Moreover, in the third step, for ${}^{108\text{m, off}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}}$, the fact that the enhancement in going from lasers off the ${}^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance towards the ${}^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance is negligible compared to the enhancement for ${}^{107}\text{Ag}$. While for ${}^{108\text{m, on}}\varepsilon_{ion,108\text{m}}$, $\frac{{}^{108\text{m, on}}I_{108\text{m}}}{{}^{108\text{m, on}}I_{108\text{m}}} = 1$ was used.

The suppression factors for collection with the lasers configured on the ${}^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance compared to off-resonance are averaged over the whole collection to give $SF_{110\text{m, off}} = 0.01^3$ and $SF_{110\text{m, on}} = 0.2$.

³The enhancement factor for off-resonance collection is $2.36 \cdot 10^5$. The difference between the suppression factor and the enhancement factor is explained by the mass separator, i.e., after the laser ionization the purity has increased by a factor $1/0.01 = 100$, the remaining increase in purity ($2.36 \cdot 10^3$) corresponds to the purity enhancement coming from the mass separator. This value corresponds closely to the expected value of 2500.

3.4 Self-sputtering

During the implantation, every implanted particle counts, but particles can be lost from the foil after being implanted due to *self-sputtering*. Self-sputtering occurs when the momentum of the impinging ion is transferred to nuclei in the collection foil, causing a nuclear collision cascade that can eject surface nuclei, i.e., these nuclei are sputtered out of the foil. As the implantation is started, the foil material nuclei will be sputtered out of the foil, hence the surface of the foil will approach the earlier implanted isotopes. Consequently, these earlier implanted isotopes eventually reach the surface, so that they can be *self-sputtered* from the foil.

Both $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ and ^{107}Ag will contribute to self-sputtering. Hence, the fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ of the beam implanted on the foil will influence the collection time and the amount of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ that can be collected given the amount of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ present in the target. Moreover, as self-sputtering is regulated by the incoming fluence, i.e. the number of incoming particles per area, the implantation spot has a large influence on the self-sputtering. Therefore, beam-rastering can be employed at the GLM collection point to obtain an increased implantation spot. The glassy carbon foils have a radius of 8 mm enabling an inscribed square of length 11 mm. Hence, the beam-rastering can be configured such that implantation is performed uniformly over 1 cm^2 .

To quantitatively assess the impact of self-sputtering, TRIDYN simulations were conducted for silver implantation in carbon at 30 keV, as illustrated in Figure 13. Both the simulated curve and a rescaled curve derived from gold implantation results are shown. The rescaled curve is translated along the $y = x$ line compared to the simulated curve. This shift is determined by comparing the simulated curve for Au-implantation in glassy carbon to an experimental data point. It is essential to note that only one experimental data point for gold implantation is available for benchmarking the simulations. Therefore, the achieved rescaling provides only a coarse zeroth order correction and experimental verification of the silver self-sputtering curve should be considered.

Figure 13: Number of retained silver particles as a function of the incoming number of silver particles for implantation performed with a uniform implantation spot of 1 cm^2 . Both the result of the simulation and the result rescaled to the experimental point of gold implantation are shown.

With this self-sputtering curve, the number of particles required in the target can subsequently be determined, given the number of particles that need to be retained on the foil.

3.5 Expected fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$, collection time and needed number of particles in the target

From the preceding analysis, the fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ that is expected in the collection foil can be calculated from the initial fraction in the target ($\frac{N(^{108\text{m}})}{N(^{108\text{m}})+N(^{107})}$). The expected fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ is determined as follows

$$\text{fraction of } ^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag in collection foil} = \frac{N(^{108\text{m}}, \text{foil})}{N(^{108\text{m}}, \text{foil}) + N(^{107}, \text{foil})} \quad (11)$$

$$= EF \cdot \text{initial fraction of } ^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag in target.} \quad (12)$$

Where EF, the laser ionization enhancement factor, is taken as $6.17 \cdot 10^4$ for lasers on-resonance for $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$. For lasers off-resonance, EF equals $2.84 \cdot 10^5$, in both cases, the worst case value is taken to ensure the feasibility of the future $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ collection.

Additionally, the collection time is calculated as the total charge of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ ions to be collected divided by the ion load limit in terms of the $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ current with lasers on or off the $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance. The total charge that has to be collected is calculated from the self-sputtering graph (taking into account the total number of silver particles, i.e. $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag} + ^{107}\text{Ag}$).

Finally, the number of particles needed in the target to achieve a specific number of particles on the collection foil is computed. First, the number of particles impinging on the foil is determined from the number of particles that must be retained on the foil using the self-sputtering curve. Then, the number of particles needed in the target is determined by dividing the number of required particles impinging on the foil by the collection efficiency. The collection efficiency for collection with the lasers on and off the $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance is 3.25% and 1.16%, respectively.

An overview of the expected time to collect and fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ on the foil as a function of the fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ in the target is shown in Figure 14. Additionally, Figure 15 depicts the number of particles needed in the target as a function of the number of required particles on the foil. It is inferred that the time needed to collect increases as the fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ decreases due to ion load limits restricting the rate of ion implantation. Hence, if the fraction of ^{107}Ag compared to $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ is larger, ion load limits are reached earlier as a function of the $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ current. Moreover, considering self-sputtering, more particles need to be collected than are retained in the foil. Consequently, more particles are needed in the target and the time to collect increases. On top of that, a hard limit on the amount of retained particles is present and exceeding this limit decreases drastically the number of retained particles. Additionally, the influence of lasers on and off the $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ resonance can be considered. Although this might seem counter-intuitive at first, for lasers on resonance, the collection time increases due to a smaller reduction of the ^{109}Ag current, making ion load limits more restrictive. Conversely, for collection with lasers on-resonance, fewer particles are needed in the target due to increased efficiency compared to collections with lasers off resonance.

Figure 14: The collection time that is needed to collect $3.15 \cdot 10^{16}$ particles, if the collection is performed at a current equal to the onset of ion load effects, as a function of the fraction of ^{108m}Ag in the target. Additionally in the graph below, the fraction of ^{108m}Ag that is expected on the foil as a function of the fraction of ^{108m}Ag in the target is shown. The yellow line indicates collection on-resonance of ^{108m}Ag , while the red line indicates collection off resonance of ^{108m}Ag . The colored dashed lines show the result if no self-sputtering would be present. In the upper plot, the black dashed lines indicate the 1 day, 5 day and 1 month mark. In the second plot the dashed line represents the fraction of ^{108m}Ag that is needed to perform muonic x-ray spectroscopy.

Figure 15: The number of particles that is needed in the target as a function of the number of particles that should be collected on the foil. Both the results for a target fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ of $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and 1%. The yellow line indicates collection on-resonance of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$, while the red line indicates collection off resonance of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$. The dashed line shows the result if no self-sputtering would be present.

4 Plan for the next collection

Based on the analysis that was performed, ideal conditions for collecting enough material with high enough fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ to do muonic x-ray spectroscopy at PSI are put forward:

Irradiation of **100mg** enriched ^{107}Ag to a fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ of **1%** (corresponding to $5.63 \cdot 10^{18}$ $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ particles) and collection at ISOLDE-GLM in **off-resonance laser mode**.

This would yield:

- fraction of $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ on collection foil = 99.96%
- $6.5(2) \cdot 10^{16}$ $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ particles incoming on the foil
- $\approx 3.1(1) \cdot 10^{16}$ $^{108\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ particles retained on the foil (at most $\approx 3.6 \cdot 10^{16}$, if collection is stopped at the maximum of the self-sputtering curve)
- A collection time at ISOLDE-GLM of ≈ 1.63 days

Additionally, some future steps are listed of what should be considered before the final collection or during the final collection.

- Frequency is crucial → Credo laser can be stabilized, but LiopStar laser not, investigation in closing the shutter when laser drifts too much towards on resonance with ^{107}Ag .
- It is important to stop on time with the collection so that we end at the maximum of the self-sputtering curve.
- Investigate γ -ray spectroscopy at the collection point (rate estimate with a HPGe detector should be investigated).

At this time, we have been informed that the ILL high-flux irradiation point is fully booked in 2024 and cannot be used. Contact has been taken with BR2 (SCK CEN) and MARIA (Polatom) to ask whether such an irradiation would be possible in 2024.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the ISOLDE collaboration and technical teams for their support.

These activities are supported by a KU Leuven BOF grant (C14/22/104); by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) under grants 05K22PGA and 05K22PGB; by the European Commission Horizon 2020 Framework, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action, Innovative Training Network LISA (no. 861198); by the European Commission Horizon Europe Framework, Research and Innovation Programme EUROLABS (no. 101057511); and by FWO.

A Experimental protocol

In this appendix, the most important experimental information is combined for later reference during the 'real' collection.

A.1 At the collection point

A.1.1 How to take out a sample

To extract a sample at GLM, the procedure necessitates the presence of two people. Specifically, one person designated as "clean-hands" person cannot come in contact with contaminated material. Simultaneously, a second individual, identified as the "dirty-hands" person, is permitted to handle surfaces that may be contaminated.

1. Check that both beam line valves are closed (extra check at the top of the setup by feeling with finger in the hole to see if tube is in or out) (performed by the dirty hands person)
2. Switch off the high voltage on the electron suppression shield (performed by the dirty hands person)
3. Isolate the turbopump from the chamber by turning the valve (clockwise) (performed by the dirty hands person)
4. Check that the pressure measurement device is off (performed by the dirty hands person)

5. Purge the chamber multiple times:
 - (a) Vent the chamber (performed by the dirty hands person)
 - (b) Make pre-vacuum (check that the red valve is in the right direction to use the pre-vacuum pump) (performed by the dirty hands person)
 - (c) Vent the chamber (performed by the dirty hands person)
 - (d) Make pre-vacuum (performed by the dirty hands person)
 - (e) Vent the chamber (performed by the dirty hands person)
6. Open the collection chamber (dirty hands person opens chamber while clean hands softly lays down the window)
7. Using the tweezers, the dirty person takes the sample out and puts it in the container that is held by the clean hands person.
8. Clean hands person walks with the container towards the fume hood while dirty hands person checks themselves for contamination
9. Dirty hands person takes out the sample in the fume hood. **Important:** the container cannot touch the inside of the fume hood
10. Dirty hands person checks themselves for contamination
11. Dirty hands person puts new sample inside
12. Make pre-vacuum using the pre-vacuum pump (wait until the pressure is $\approx 10^{-2}$ mbar) (performed by the clean hands person)
13. Turn the red valve such that now the turbopump tube is connected to the chamber (performed by the clean hands person)
14. Open the turbopump connection (anti-clockwise) (performed by the clean hands person)
15. Turn on high-voltage for the electron suppression shield (performed by the clean hands person)

A.2 Working Set Launcher

- **Change mass on mass separator:** GPS → mass control → put isotope → press enter → press send
- **HV control:** via HTControl
- **Heat the target:** GPS → target heating → select current and steps to increase with → press start
- **Mass scan:** GPS → mass scan
- **If target trips (target temperature will be 0A):** Go to WorkingSets → Separators → frontend → power the supply of the target (YGPS.targetheat) and start to heat. **Important:** do not press write EQP to buffer, in that case the default settings are gone

- **If high voltage drops:** GPS → HTControl GPS to restart it
- **If lost deflector settings:** Go to General → Eqp array → set: write buffer to EQP, such that the values of the deflectors are brought back to their default values
- **If something happens:** check that in WorkingSet → separators, the "ISO:GLM" is active, in the SEP tab the first 4 values are ok if they are red, but if something else is red, it means that it has tripped and thus we should:
 - right click on red value and chose contr
 - select Mode
 - select Reset
 - select ON
- Total beam FC: YGPS.BFC0600
- Separated beam FC: YGPS.BFC4900 and YGLM.BFC0900
- **Important:** never measure total beam while blaze laser is on!

A.3 Taking beam in GLM

Important: the deflector and BFC4900 cannot be in together. The deflector is in (position = 418) when it sends beam to GLM and the deflector is out if it is at position 200 (sending beam to GPS instead of GLM)

LOGIN computer: Username: SSP; password: Hyper\$ine21

1. Close the beam gate (from the rack in the old control room (manually), not possible from the computer, see Figure 16)

Figure 16: Beam gate switch

2. Close the two beam valves in the GLM beamline
3. Check that BFC4900 is not in
4. Change deflector position from 200 (beam to GPS) to position 418 (beam to GLM)
5. Set the right position of the sample holder and set magnet on the right mass
6. Open the beam gate
7. Beam sweeping is controlled with Inspector 3.5.51-Sweeping
8. Current implanted on the foil can be followed with the Current Integrator panel. To start it, press the red "Zero Check is ON" button (it should become green and show "Zero Check is OFF")
9. Start sweeping, open the two beam valves in the GLM beam line and press start in the Current Integrator panel

A.4 Laser control

Rilis-vm

Control of the lasers (ON/OFF, not the frequency)

Press right click → tools → Remmina → rilis-vm → username: rilis; password: Tisa-dye23

Rilis-pxi

Control of the blaze: icon with the star

Important: Do not turn on the blaze while the total beam Faraday cup is in

Press right click → tools → Remmina → rilis-pxi → username: rilis; password: Tisa-dye23

Rilis-control

Shows the current values of all laser frequencies + control of LiopStar laser (via LiopStar Control) + the Credo laser (via SirahControl)

signal 1 = laser 1a; signal 2 = laser 1b; signal 3 = laser for the second step

Press right click → tools → Remmina → rilis-control → username: rilis; password: Tisa-dye23

Frequency scan In rilis-control:

1. turn off laser 1b
2. go to StartMenuShortcuts folder
3. XY logger → "Shared Variable XY logger with memory-shortcut"
4. x-value: ni.var.psp: rilisW6 → HighFinessWavemeterWS6 → Wavenumber channel (this is to scan laser 1a)
5. y-value: ni.var.psp → localhost → ISOLDE Device Readout Shared Variable → GPS FC490 Ion Beam current
6. click on Logging (will become orange) and then on the arrow to start the measurement
7. go to Sirah control to change the frequency of the Credo (1a) laser
8. To find file: press "open log Folder"

References

- [1] R Catherall, W Andreazza, M Breitenfeldt, A Dorsival, GJ Focker, TP Gharsa, TJ Giles, JL Grenard, F Locci, P Martins, et al. The isolde facility. *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics*, 44(9):094002, 2017.
- [2] Valentin Fedosseev, Katerina Chrysalidis, Thomas Day Goodacre, Bruce Marsh, Sebastian Rothe, Christoph Seiffert, and Klaus Wendt. Ion beam production and study of radioactive isotopes with the laser ion source at isolde. *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics*, 44(8):084006, 2017.